

LINGUACULTURAL ASPECTS OF VERBS SENSE PERCEPTION IN THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *In connection with the rise of foreign language teaching to the level of state policy in the period of independence, the training of qualified foreign language teachers and translators for our country, textbooks, manuals, language theories, foreign language in accordance with modern requirements. There is a need to redevelop and develop the teaching and learning of the Uzbek language in the Uzbek audience. In particular, in this article I would like to describe the sensory verbs in Uzbek and English.*

Keywords: *sense, perception, foreign languages, linguacultural aspects, hear, see, taste, smell, feel.*

O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA FE'LLARNING HIS TUYG'USINING LINGVOMADANIY JIHATLARI

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Annotatsiya: *Mustaqillik davrida chet tillarni o'qitishning davlat siyosati darajasiga ko'tarilishi munosabati bilan mamlakatimiz uchun malakali chet tili o'qituvchilari va tarjimonlar tayyorlash, zamonaviy talablar asosida darsliklar, o'quv qo'llanmalar, til nazariyalari, chet tili. . O'zbek auditoriyasida o'zbek tilini o'qitish va o'rganishni qayta ko'rib chiqish va rivojlantirish zarur. Jumladan, ushbu maqolada men o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi sezgi fe'llariga ta'rif bermoqchiman.*

Kalit so'zlar: *His qilish, idrok etish, chet tillari, lingvamadaniy jihatlar, eshitish, ko'rish, ta'm, hidlash, his qilish.*

It is noteworthy that the President said that “the state language is becoming an active means of communication at the international level. In particular, we are all proud of the growing role and importance of the Uzbek language in meetings and talks with foreign leaders, negotiations, signing ceremonies, prestigious summits, and official press conferences. At present, great importance is attached to the study and teaching of foreign languages in our country. This, of course, is not in vain. There is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our country, which today is striving to take its rightful place in the world community, and for our people, who are

building their great future in terms of foreign partners. The comparative study of Uzbek languages is of great importance in the search for and discovery of unexplored aspects of both languages. A comparative study of languages reveals features that have been overlooked in the study of one language, i.e., some of the features that the linguist did not pay attention to when studying one language become apparent when comparing two languages. This helps to identify the difficulties of the comparable foreign language for foreign language learners. Interlingual similarities and differences, on the other hand, mean that differences cause interference, similarities create facilitations, make it easier for a language learner to learn another language, and lead to mistakes or communication interruptions. Identifying the specific trends and patterns of the languages being compared, the mutual enrichment of the languages being compared with each other, and the interactions and alternatives are also theoretical issues that arise as a result of comparing the two languages. Therefore, comparative linguistics is the linguodidactic basis of foreign language teaching, that is, the methodological significance of the differences and similarities in the compared languages is determined by the interlinguistic interventions and facilitations that occur in the speech of foreign language learners shows the difficult and easy aspects for Uzbek students.

In many English and Uzbek grammars, a number of characters developed without taking into account the latest achievements of linguistics have escaped the attention of English and Uzbek linguists in the classification of verbs and have been interpreted differently. Developed and classified without taking into account the necessary principles of grammatical categories such as time, ratio and inclination. This principle should be developed taking into account the relationship between grammar and vocabulary in the classification of verb types. A verb is a group of words that express the meaning of an action and answer questions such as what did (happened) ?, what does (do) happen ?, what does (will happen?). . For example: The student studied (what did he/she do?). Like the cars roar (what does it do?).

Each of the above verb types contains several verbs. These verbs differ in how they express the meaning of the action. The following differences can be observed:

1. Distinguish between strengths and weaknesses: smile - laugh.
2. According to the positive and negative values: laugh - smile; to speak is to murmur, to mutter.
3. According to the stylistic features: to laugh (a common word) - to smile (a common style), to speak (a common word) - to create a speech (a common style).

Using each of the above verbs in their proper place ensures fluency, clarity, and expressiveness in speech. Now, we come to the part where we talk about the middle ground. What is sense perception in general?

Man perceives the world through his senses and strives for it. With the help of the senses, he embodies what he feels. For example, you watch TV, in which a dancer dances, and you get spiritual pleasure by watching her dance. Or when you read a work of art, you feel it in your imagination while you read it with your eyes, you create it with those heroes. There are so many examples of sensory verbs around us because our daily lives are all about feeling and feeling. There are so many forms of expression in our language, because our Uzbek language is rich and we can find 10 meanings of each word. Language is a great gift created by man and "gifted" to man. There is language, there is communication, there

is history, there is culture and literature. The perfection and development of language is closely connected with the rise of fiction. The realization of language as an opportunity in speech, the fact that it occurs through speech, the dialectical relationship between language and speech takes place in the word - the unity of language and speech. So language is expressed through speech, and speech is expressed through the richness of language. Linguistic richness is mainly words (lexemes) that have sound and meaning in terms of form and content. The word has a social-practical scientific significance with these two aspects.

The semantic structure of a word is directly related to its meaning (sema). It is because there is no meaning without a semantic structure. Each meaning is "evaluated" according to its semantic structure and experience. The fact that a particular word forms the content side, together with the sound base, the expression side, plays a specific role in language and speech as a whole. More precisely, the meaning is the spiritual essence - the phenomenon of consciousness has its own external (extralinguistic) basis. The objective being, which forms the basis of the word of each independent meaning, has its own natural structure, the members of its construction, each of which has its own natural structure, members, each of which has a linguistic name (word) in the literal sense. The meaning of a word, the structure of meaning, consists of certain logical parts, components (semas). These logical components form the meaning of a word, ensuring that each meaning exists as a separate linguistic "unit". The components of a word carry a specific message in speech. This means that the small logical, components of the meaning of a word are in a mutually stable whole (system) relationship and serve as a verbal (expression) of meaning. To study the semantic structure of the word, to analyze, to determine the logical parts of the meaning of the word, to determine the types of its components, to explain the place and significance of each semant in the semantic structure to reveal the relation to the semantics - to find the logical connection between the meanings (to form the semantic syntagm) allow you to identify semaphores that differ from each other. The results of this are of great scientific and practical importance for semiotics, lexicography, lexicology, and linguists in general. Therefore, it is important to study the semantic structure of English verbs, including intuitive verbs. When we think about the semantic structure of intuitive verbs in English - the structure of meaning, the analysis of the meaning of the verb reveals its components, logical parts (semaphores), and on this basis the meaning of the verb explained. Intuitive verbs represent the state of human perception. Let's classify the sensory verbs in English as follows.

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